

tion showed cytoplasm vacuolation, and coagulation followed by hyphae bursting.

Bacteria with different colony types were isolated from sheath blight sclerotia and tested in petri dishes to study their antagonistic activities against *T. cucumeris*. Many isolates were antagonistic. Some inhibited mycelial growth and caused browning of hyphal tips. Microscopic examination showed that necrosis of hyphae occurred. Hyphae remained intact but nonviable, and protoplasm was agglutinated and pigmented.

Isolate 17 prevented lesion develop

Effect of antagonistic bacteria on incidence and severity of sheath blight in the IRRI greenhouse.^a

Treatment	Incidence ^b (%)	Severity (lesion length, cm)
Isolate 17 + pathogen	30	0.61
Isolate 24 + pathogen	75	1.27
Pathogen alone	100	2.00

Bacterial suspension (1×10^6 cells/ml) was sprayed at the basal portion 1 day before inoculation. ^bIncidence based on number of tillers infected divided by total number of tillers: 3 hills/replication; 3 replications/treatment.

ment when sprayed on detached rice flag leaves before, after, and simultaneously

with inoculation of the pathogen. Sclerotial bodies soaked in a suspension of bacterial isolate 17 for 2 weeks were not viable. Bodies treated with isolate 24 showed an abrupt germination decline (63.3% to 26.7%) at 0 and 2-week sampling periods. Twenty percent of the sclerotia soaked in isolate 24 for 6 weeks were viable.

Preliminary greenhouse test results showed isolate 17 sprayed at the basal portion of the rice plants 1 day before inoculation was superior to isolate 24 for reducing sheath blight incidence and inhibiting lesion development (see table). ✎

Host range of rice gall dwarf virus

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A new rice virus disease that causes stunting, dark green leaf discoloration,

and presence of galls along the leaf blades and leaf sheaths was identified as rice gall dwarf virus (RGDV) in Thailand in 1979.

Second- and third-instar nymphs of rice green leafhopper *Nephotettix nigropictus* that had fed on infected rice plants for 2 to 3 days were reared on healthy TN1 seedlings for 10 to 14 days, then *N. nigropictus* was used to inoculate 11 plant species grown in pots: maize *Zea mays*, sorghum *Sorghum nervosum*, timothy grass *Phleum pratense*, orchard grass *Dactylis glomerata*, Italian rye-grass *Lolium multiflorum*, Japanese grass *Alopecurus aequalis* var. *amurensis*, wild rice *Oryza rufipogon*, barley *Hordeum distichum*, wheat *Triticum aestivum*, rye *Secale cereale*, and oat *Avena sativa*. At the second leaf

stage seedling were inoculated by placing 2 viruliferous insects on each plant for 2 to 3 days.

Virus symptoms developed 15 to 30 days after inoculation. Inoculated plants were examined by electron microscope using a negative stain preparation, then were back-inoculated to healthy rice seedlings. Barley, wheat, rye, oat, Italian ryegrass, Japanese grass, and wild rice showed typical symptoms. Polyhedral particles 65 nm in diameter were observed in the negatively stained preparation. Rice plants exhibited symptoms after back-inoculation.

Maize, sorghum, timothy grass, and orchard grass did not show symptoms. No particles were observed under the electron microscope, nor did symptoms appear after back-inoculation. ✎

Weed host of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, a rice sheath blight pathogen

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During July 1982 *Echinochloa colona*, a common rice field weed, was severely

infected with *R. solani* in some fields in the Cooch Behar district of West Bengal and the Goalpara district of Assam.

Both areas are in high-rainfall zones (more than 300 cm/year). The infected weed was growing in rice fields with 20-25 cm standing water, and on the boun-

dary ridges of the fields. Soil pH was between 5.5 and 6.5. Rice plants were moderately affected by the disease.

R. solani isolates from this weed species have been found to infect artificially inoculated rice. ✎

Decline in number and viability of sclerotia of rice stem rot fungus in soil

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Sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae* Catt., the causal pathogen of rice stem rot disease, were produced on a sterile rice-rice hull mixture and used to artificially infest soil from a wet fallow field.

Seventy-nine mg of sclerotia were weighed and mixed thoroughly into 3 kg

of sandy loam soil in pots by sprinkling the sclerotia on the soil surface and thoroughly mixing the soil using a hand-operated rototiller. Propagules (sclerotia) were introduced at the rate of about 5 sclerotia/g of soil, which corresponds to a moderate infestation level. There

were three replications using two amendments. Chopped and dried rice and mustard *Brassica campestris* var. *Sarson* straws were added to equal 2% of the soil. Pots were located in normal field conditions and watered occasionally to supplement rainfall and provide average annual precipitation.

Soil columns were sampled at the end of the month using a standard soil-core sampler 2 cm in diameter and 18 cm deep. At each sample date, five soil cores were collected from each treatment, bulked in a paper bag, and air-dried in the laboratory. Five 50-g subsamples were taken from each bag and sclerotia were recovered by washing over 20- and 100-mesh screens. Sclerotia from each treatment were counted under a dissecting microscope and viability was tested by growing them on water agar supplemented with streptomycin sulfate and penicillin at 3,000 ppm each under constant fluorescent light at 25±2° C.

Presence of organic matter reduced sclerotia survival — percent viability of sclerotia was less although total number

1. Effect of organic amendments on decline of sclerotia number.

2. Effect of organic amendments on germination of sclerotia.

of sclerotia had increased or remained constant over time. Burying sclerotia for 8 months in the presence of mustard reduced their number by 76% (Fig. 1) and viability by 75% (Fig. 2). Number and viability also declined in treatments without amendment, but after a few months germination ability stabilized at about 50%. Rice straw amendment

decreased number and viability in the beginning, but sclerotia increased at the end of the burial period (Fig. 1).

Rice residue seems to be a major factor in increasing the *S. oryzae* inoculum level in field soil. However, application of mustard organic matter will substantially reduce the inoculum level in the field.

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice yield losses to gall midge in North Thailand

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Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is one of the most economically important insect pests of rainfed wetland rice in Thailand. Granular insecticides are the only effective means of control, but they are expensive and require multiple applications to obtain satisfactory results. Gall midge infestations vary in Thailand and insecticide application should be based on the use of an economic threshold.

Experiments in farmers' fields at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, assessed yield losses caused by gall midge. A conventional

Gall midge infestation, yield components, and yield losses of 4 rice varieties at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, Thailand. 1979-81.^a

Variety	Insecticide treatment ^b	Infested tillers (%) 55-65 DT	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
1979						
RD1	Treated	1.0	11.4	5.5	2.3	—
RD1	Untreated	21.5	12.0	4.4	1.9	19
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Treated	2.2	10.7	4.6	2.7	—
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Untreated	26.5	10.9	4.4	2.5	8
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Treated	0.4	10.1	5.7	2.0	—
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Untreated	19.2	10.7	4.9	1.8	10
Leaung-Laung	Treated	1.8	7.1	4.5	2.9	—
Leaung-Laung	Untreated	25.0	11.5	3.1	1.9	33
1980						
RD1	Treated	6.3	9.7	6.0	1.8	—
RD1	Untreated	71.5	13.7	3.2	0.9	52
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Treated	1.4	8.1	6.0	2.5	—
Niew-San-Pahtawng	Untreated	68.9	11.1	3.8	1.5	42
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Treated	1.4	9.6	6.0	1.9	—
Dawk-Ma-Li 105	Untreated	73.7	11.8	3.5	0.9	49
Leaung-Laung	Treated	0.6	8.1	5.7	2.5	—
Leaung-Laung	Untreated	61.1	12.2	3.6	1.2	50
1981						
RD1	Treated	9.8	11.8	8.9	3.1	—
RD1	Untreated	28.7	13.8	8.8	2.5	17

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